

Threats to Biodiversity: An Ecocritical Approach to Anuradha Roy's *The Folded Earth*

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Received: May 27, 2025

Accepted: Jun 22, 2025

Published: Jun 24, 2025

Abstract— This research paper explores the threats to biodiversity through an ecocritical lens, using Anuradha Roy's *The Folded Earth*. The novel is set against the backdrop of the Himalayan foothills, an ecologically significant and delicate ecosystem. By examining themes of deforestation, urbanization, wildlife displacement, anthropocentric human activities, it analyses how Roy's work depicts environmental degradation, and explores in what way human activities are becoming threats to biodiversity. This paper sheds light on how literature can raise awareness on the burning issue and to advocate the preservation of biodiversity. This paper mainly focuses on how *The Folded Earth* addresses various threats to biodiversity and reflects the ecological imbalances as a result of anthropocentrism. The research attempts to study the novel and environmental reality parallelly to understand how fiction can mirror and magnify the challenges faced by ecosystems in the modern world.

Keywords— biodiversity, ecocriticism, anthropocentric,

I. INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity, i.e., biological diversity is the richness of variability of life on earth. Biodiversity includes all living organisms, from the smallest microorganisms to the largest mammals, as well as the complex ecological systems they form. (Lévêque, 2003; Gaston, 2004) This richness of life is essential for the stability and sustainability of ecosystems. It forms the backbone of the earth's ecological balance, which is important for sustainability of life on earth. This paper deals with Anuradha Roy's *The Folded Earth* and to explore the concerns about biodiversity, threats to biodiversity by studying the novel under the lens of ecocriticism.

II. THE IMPORTANCE OF BIODIVERSITY AND ITS THREATS

As highlighted in global biodiversity assessments (e.g., IPBES 2019), biodiversity loss is accelerating at an unprecedented rate, driven largely by human activities such as deforestation, habitat fragmentation, pollution, and climate change. Tamale remarks:

“The current losses of biodiversity have both direct and indirect causes. The direct causes include: 1. Habitat loss and fragmentation 2. Invasion by alien/exotic species 3. Destructive exploitation and over-use of the natural resources 4. Pollution 5. Modern agriculture/forestry 6. Natural factors - climate change, wildfires, natural disasters, etc. The indirect causes (or underlying factors) include: 1. Population growth

and high consumption rates 2. Poverty 3. Inappropriate macroeconomic policies 4. Inequity in resource ownership/management and benefit-sharing 5. Deficiencies in knowledge and its application 6. Poor policies and bad institutional arrangements.” (WWF IPBES Report 2019)

Humankind’s unending desire for economy and power, increasingly causes threats to biodiversity, ultimately ending up in biodiversity loss. Majorly, Overexploitation of resources results in climate change, and global warming. Several authors have critically examined these challenges. In *Silent Spring*, Rachel Carson highlighted the detrimental effects of pesticides on wildlife, particularly birds, bringing attention to how chemical pollutants can cause widespread ecological harm. Vandana Shiva, in *Staying Alive: Women, Ecology and Development*, discussed the interconnectedness of ecological degradation and socio-economic factors, emphasizing how development policies can marginalize both women and the environment. Edward O. Wilson, through *The Diversity of Life*, explored the intricate web of life and the consequences of biodiversity loss, advocating for conservation strategies to preserve Earth's biological richness.

Further, in Rob Nixon’s *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor*, the causes of biodiversity loss in a slow pace are being discussed. Nixon discusses Kenya's Green Belt Movement and India’s Chipko movement that emerged against the government and private agencies that overexploited the forest resources. It criticises the stance of the government that holds sovereignty over the landscapes, nature, and its people for the materialistic supremacy and power.

“For the Kenyan and Indian protestors, active reforestation became the primary symbolic vehicle for their civil disobedience....To Kenya’s authoritarian president, the forest was state owned, and because he and his cronies treated the nation as identical to the state, he felt at license to sell national forests and sell off the nation’s public land. To the activists, by contrast, the forest was not a private presidential fiefdom, but commonage, the indivisible property of the people. The regime’s contemptuous looting of Karura Forest was thus read as symptomatic of a wider contempt for the rights of the poor” (*Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor,2011*)

III. THE FOLDED EARTH UNDER ECOCRITICAL LENS

Anuradha Roy is an eminent prolific writer. Her versatility displayed through various genres like novels, nonfiction works, newspaper articles etc. She has marked her debut novels through *An Atlas of Impossible Longing* (2008), *The Folded Earth* (2011), *Sleeping on Jupiter* (2015), *All the Lives We Never Lived* (2018), and *The Earthspinner* (2021). Roy’s themes range from identity, love and loss, nature, and memory, most prominently exploring the human relationships with nature.

Anuradha Roy's *The Folded Earth* portrays the deep connection between human and nature and explores various themes, most prominently, the interconnectedness of the human and non-human entities. This novel set in the Himalayan town of Ranikhet, the narrative follows Maya, a young widow seeking solace after her husband's tragic demise. Through the major characters, Roy highlights how anthropocentric activities contribute to exploitation of nature, encroachment of urban development, and recreational activities into the pristine Ranikhet mirrors the human intrusion into the natural ecosystems. The depletion of natural resources and the transformation of the landscape not only destabilize the cultural and economic fabric of the society but also threaten the ecological balance.

Through vivid descriptions of the landscape and the lives of its inhabitants, Roy delves into themes of environmental degradation, the impact of modernization, and the symbiotic connection between nature and human existence. This novel portrays Ranikhet as a serene and ecologically rich area, which has lush forests and diverse wildlife forming an integral part of the local people's daily life.

The *Folded Earth*, the story centres around the important characters Maya, the protagonist, - a widowed young woman, her demised husband Michael, and Veer, and other minor characters. However, Roy portrayed all the characters in the novel as associated with nature either in positive terms or in negative terms. Roy projects this connection in a natural way and fosters the dualism of human-nonhuman diversity throughout the novel. The way the novel progresses can resonate with the reality of how human interests impact biodiversity. Consequently, it displays the dynamics of the potential threats for biodiversity parallel to its plotline.

Roy portrayed the locals as close to nature; they cherish the environment with super sanctity. This is expressed through the voice of one of the vital characters of the novel, Diwan Sahib "*The mountains do not reveal themselves to the people who come here merely to escape the heat of the plains... The peaks emerge for those devoted to them through the coldest of the winters and the wettest of monsoons.*" (*The Folded Earth*). The narration gives the details that the locals of the town Ranikhet lead a simple lifestyle that is closely connected to nature. Their daily activities reflect a natural harmony with their surroundings, they care for animals, landscapes and their environment. Though they may not be consciously aware of ecological concepts or scientific terms like "biodiversity" and "sustainability," their way of life inherently supports and preserves the local ecosystem. One of the important characters of the novel Puran, a person with intellectual disability is very close to nature and animals, he understands the animal language. This unconscious environmental consciousness reveals that traditional lifestyles, rooted in nature, can contribute significantly to the conservation of biodiversity. However, Roy also portrayed the contrast to this by the characters that are in positions of power like administrator Mr. Chauhan and politicians and

individuals seeking control disrupting this balance for personal or political gain. Their interventions, driven by the desire to exercise authority or exploit resources, threaten the local, in turn it affects the very ecological harmony that the local community maintains unknowingly but effectively. Additionally, Roy depicts the commercialization effects, tourism, and alteration of landscape which contributes biodiversity loss to an extended level through *“Ranikhet has to become the Switzerland of India... The lush greenery that beautified the pavements was ousted to furnish them with grey slabs and set up concrete benches.”* (*The Folded Earth*)

The Folded Earth effectively portrays the impacts of urbanization and its effect of extinction of species, displacement of animals and decline of ecosystem through the voice of Diwan Sahib,

“Until humans came and made anthills out of these mountains, Diwan Sahib was saying, looking up at the langurs, the land had belonged to these monkeys, and to barking deer, nilgai, tiger, barasingha, leopards, jackals, the great horned owl, and even to cheetahs and lions.” In addition to this, it depicts the deforestation effects due to urbanisation, the government’s prioritization only on infrastructure development, focuses on anthropocentric ideologies and does not much bother about balancing the ecosystem which are the rationale for the biodiversity loss, *“The forest was being cut down in patches, and the hillside was being scraped off to make a road, though no one knew where it led.”* Further, Roy expresses the locals' distress due to the tourism and seasonal human intrusion as *“The tourists had gone, and the summer visitors with them. Only now does our town feel truly ours, as if it has been rescued from intruders and returned to us.”* (*The Folded Earth*)

IV. CONCLUSION

In essence, *The Folded Earth* serves as a tool to stress on the necessity of environmental consciousness and the importance of the ties between human life and the natural world. Roy's narrative encourages readers to understand the impact of modernization on ecological systems and the importance of preserving the delicate balance that sustains both nature and humanity. Through powerful imagery the novel captures the irreversible loss of biodiversity, the slow extinction of species, and disruption for the local ecosystem. Roy’s portrayal of wildlife disappearance, vanity of forests alarms the urgent need for understanding the current violence practices, and the need of new policies to recover the ecosystem. *The Folded Earth* invites the readers to reconsider the human relationship with nature in order to acknowledge the silent sufferings embedded within the landscapes in terms of power and progress.

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